

SELECTION OF FAIRY TALES FOR TEACHING ENGLISH TO PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Annotation. Many adults love fairy tales, especially children. Fairy tales in English are a great way to further stimulate a child's interest in a foreign language and diversify the educational process. Fairy tales have great educational potential.

Keywords: fairy tale, preschool education, English language, method, teaching.

INTRODUCTION

Fairy tales help the child develop an appropriate attitude towards the surrounding reality, the actions of people, cause the desire to imitate the good and resist the bad.

A fairy tale for a child is, first of all, a means of understanding the world, a way of forming an active worldview. The tale teaches bright and strong human feelings, it offers a path on which you can find your happiness. The story amuses, touches, captivates. But with all this, she invariably raises questions; the fairy tale wants the child to think.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Fairy tales are a wonderful means of introducing children to the culture of peoples, to the development of speech. They turn the process of learning English into an attractive game. In many of the tales, there is a compositional technique typical of folklore - repetition. Each episode, enriched with a new detail, repeats almost verbatim the previous one, which helps to recognize words and gradually forms the skill of perceiving the text. Even with a relatively small vocabulary, a fairy tale allows the child to feel that he can speak English. English becomes a means of

communication. When using a fairy tale, the process of forming speaking skills is aimed at developing readiness for communication, at using a foreign language as a means of communication. The fairy tale contributes to the inclusion of children in the process of communication. On the content basis of a fairy tale, various situations of game role-playing communication, plot-role-playing games, and dialogues can be built.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The undoubted advantages of a fairy tale are that it:

- firstly, it contributes to the formation of learning motivation;
- secondly, it increases the educational and educational opportunities of a foreign language;
- thirdly, it is an excellent means of teaching foreign language communication.

Work with fairy tales with preschool children should begin with Russian folk tales that are well known to children. You can invite the child to listen to a fairy tale in English and translate it into Uzbek (the game "Translator").

When choosing English fairy tales, it is necessary to remember their differences from Russian fairy tales. The defining difference lies in the behavior of the characters, the motives of their actions. In English folk tales, heroes do not strive to reach unprecedented heights, defeat everyone in the world, take possession of untold riches and at the same time become smarter, stronger, etc., which in Russian fairy tales most often happens to heroes. English fairy-tale characters are more inert, for them the main goal is to avoid failure, and not to succeed. But a good end in magical and everyday English fairy tales is far from always found. The endings of English fairy tales are sometimes even cruel, but, nevertheless, such a denouement is most often expected and taken for granted.

English fairy tales are very informative. Instead of magic, here often comes some dryness in the presentation of certain facts, as if the fairy tale is simply called upon to convey some information to the reader.

The narration of fairy tales is usually smooth without any unexpected plot twists.

English fairy tales about animals also differ from our Russian ones. Usually the good heroes here are the chicken and the cat, and the evil ones are the wolf and the fox.

English animal tales teach the reader to empathize with the weak, but they lack morality as such. At the same time, humor plays an important role in such fairy tales, softening acute situations and ridiculing the weak qualities of the characters. The most striking example of an English fairy tale about animals is The Three Little Pigs, known to all of us since childhood.

At the same time, in English fairy tales you can often find folk proverbs and sayings, songs and spells that allow you to feel the fabulous atmosphere of good old England.

How to read fairy tales with a child?

Tell the child the name of the story and ask them to guess what it will be about.

Read the story piece by piece. Before listening to each part, allow the installation to answer questions.

-Who is the main character

-How do we feel about it?

-What did he do

After reading, ask your child to answer the questions. Then you can use exercises like "Choose the correct answer", "Arrange pictures according to the events in the fairy tale", "Indicate the characters who say the following phrases".

The final stage after reading the fairy tale should be the speech activity of the child. To develop communication skills, you can act out dialogues, individual scenes, or even a whole fairy tale.

Games from the Magic Stickers series or a mini-theater in a chest can help you with this.

But it is best to make your own home theater with your child. For example, finger. Knitted, felt or paper - there are many options.

An interesting performance can also be arranged using a magnetic board and figures on a magnetic tape. Instead of a magnetic board, you can use a flannelograph - a base made of flannel, on which figures made of the same material are held.

CONCLUSION

Thus, telling fairy tales in different ways increases children's interest in learning English and increases the speed of learning.

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